

JOB STRESS AND WORK ENGAGEMENT AMONG DELIVERY RIDERSDela Cruz, Engracio L.¹Largado, Jess Elton C.²Makiwag, Sharelyn U.³Pintor, Apple Erm⁴Sulla, Kimberly G.⁵

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted to determine which domains of job stress best predict work engagement among delivery riders in Davao City, Philippines. The researchers used a quantitative approach, which involved the survey of a total of 110 delivery riders. The adopted survey questionnaire was the research instrument used in gathering the data. Mean, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, and Linear Regression were the statistical tools used in the study. Based on findings, delivery riders experienced a moderate level of job stress, but it did not affect their work engagement.

The results revealed no significant relationship between job stress and work engagement among the respondents. However, co-worker support has a significant influence on improving their work engagement. Their high work engagement is sustained primarily through consistent assistance, helpful advice, and feedback from their co-workers, rather than stress levels or work-life challenges. Moreover, co-worker support as the domain of job stress can singly predict work engagement.

Keywords

Job Stress, Work Engagement, Mean, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, Linear Regression, Co-worker Support, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

Work engagement has emerged as a critical factor influencing employee productivity, satisfaction, and organizational success. Being defined as a positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption (Jaya and Ariyanto, 2021). Work engagement plays a vital role in sustaining performance across industries. However, recent studies have shown a growing concern over poor work engagement, particularly in high-stress sectors such as healthcare, education, and customer service (Shahid, 2019). In recent Gallup polls, most American workers consider their jobs mediocre or awful. Around the world, the situation is much worse, with only twenty percent (20%) of workers saying they are happy with their jobs. According to a recent survey, British people's job satisfaction decreased by about 8% when compared to their average level of contentment in other areas of their lives. The only thing they associated with more unhappiness than working was being sick in bed (Maslach, and Leiter, 2022).

It was also systematically reviewed that work engagement in nursing, poor engagement, was linked to burnout, job dissatisfaction, and decreased quality of patient care. The authors emphasized that among the contributors to disengagement were the absence of supportive leadership and limited professional development opportunities. Similarly, research by Lesener, Gusy, and Wolter (2019) underscored the importance of organizational support and job resources, highlighting that poor engagement often stems from work overload, lack of autonomy, and minimal recognition.

Although job-related stress is commonly associated with negative emotional outcomes like nervousness, irritability, and psychological exhaustion, pressure at work may also be an active force that helps if harnessed. Instead of only being harmful, occupational stress can stimulate workers to improve their concentration,

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accommodate an ever-changing work environment, and practice healthy coping. Thus, Pressure at work is an engine for personal growth and creativity. Employee performance is measured as the extent to which individuals meet their duties and contribute to organizational performance, which can increase when workplace demands are addressed with resilience and support. Strategic management of workplace stress can thus promote greater motivation and commitment, ultimately leading to increased operational productivity and the realization of institutional goals (Sawar, Yasri, and Abror et al., 2020).

Among the most prominent theories outlining the connection between work engagement and job stress is the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model by Schaufeli and Bakker, established in 2004. The model presents a complete theoretical framework to understand job stress and work engagement. Work stress is created by a discrepancy between job demands and the employee's accessible resources to deal with such demands, which can affect the employee's work engagement. The JD-R model does recognize the job demands as well as the stress that can adversely affect the physical, mental, and even emotional states of the employees. Excessive demands, like heavy workloads, close deadlines, or emotionally taxing interactions, can drain employees' energy and resources, leaving them feeling overwhelmed and burned out. This stress, in turn, can have adverse effects on their engagement, making them less motivated, passionate, productive, and committed to work. The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model signifies that job stress arises from a mismatch between job demands and resources.

High demands and low resources create stress, which interferes with a positive engagement. In contrast, adequate resources protect from stress, promoting a positive engagement. It proposes that job stress arises when the demands made upon an employee do not match the available resources to meet those demands. This imbalance can affect the level of engagement of an employee directly, which in turn can result in a state of either being motivated and productive or burnout and disengagement. Hence, the JD-R model is a useful approach in explaining how job stress and work engagement relate to each other. Understanding the interaction between job demands and resources allows organizations to develop healthier and more productive working environments. This entails reducing unnecessary demands, improving job resources, and supporting employees so that they have what it takes to flourish.

METHODOLOGY

Quantitative method was applied in the research, and survey questionnaires were distributed to obtain information regarding the job stress and work engagement of delivery riders in Davao City, Philippines. The researchers themselves handed out the survey, and the delivery riders' consents were obtained prior to the distribution of the survey questionnaires. Mean, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, and Linear Regression were utilized as statistical tools in the research.

Data Collection Methods

A survey questionnaire was used in this study. The questionnaire was used in identifying the job stress and work engagement among delivery riders in Davao City, Philippines. The number of respondents involved in this study was 110, and their identities were kept confidential.

Data Analysis

A quantitative method was used in collecting the data. Mean, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, and Linear Regression were the statistical tools used in analyzing the data gathered in the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Job Stress. Presented in Table 1 is the level of job stress among delivery riders and which revealed a moderate level as reflected with a mean score of 3.38. Subsequently, they disclosed high levels for the indicators of Co-worker Support and Work-Life Balance as manifested in a mean score rating of 4.14 and 3.59 described as high respectively. However, the Delivery Riders revealed a moderate level of Job Stress and Role Expectation Conflict, as shown in a mean score rating of 3.07 and 2.78, respectively. The results imply that although delivery riders enjoy a supportive workplace environment and are able, in general, to strike a balance between work and personal life, they also occasionally experience stress in the workplace. They have, at times, heavy workload, time pressure, and pressure not to take time off. They also struggle to respond to the multiple and sometimes conflicting expectations of supervisors, colleagues, subordinates, and customers. Despite such difficulties, delivery riders consistently receive constructive advice, understanding, helpful criticism, and straightforward help from their co-workers and are to a great extent able to organize their time between work and family or personal commitments.

Table 1. Level of Job Stress among Delivery Riders

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Job Stress	0.82	3.07	Moderate
Role Expectation Conflict	0.92	2.78	Moderate
Co-worker Support	0.64	4.14	High
Work-Life Balance	0.72	3.59	High
Overall	0.49	3.38	Moderate

4.50-5.00- Very High

3.50-4.49- High

2.50-3.49- Moderate

1.50-2.49- Low

1.00-1.49- Very Low

This finding corroborates Shukla and Srivastava (2016), which posits that job stress, conflict over role expectations, co-worker support, and work-life balance are context-dependent and dynamic, and therefore highlight the need to continuously assess workplace stressors so that appropriate interventions can be taken. Particularly, the study points to how moderate levels of job stress, based on factors like vagueness of role expectations, uneven work demands, and the requirement of upholding work-life harmony, can have an enormous impact on employee well-being. Concurrently, the existence of high levels of co-worker support acts as a buffer, enabling employees to cope with stress better.

Work Engagement. Presented in Table 2 is the work engagement of delivery riders and which was revealed high level, as indicated in the mean score of 4.57. In addition, all the indicators, as expressed in the mean scores of 4.57, 4.83, and 4.39, are labeled high, respectively. It shows that delivery riders have high work engagement on all three indicators (Vigor, Dedication, Absorption). The outcome showed high vigor levels, referring to the energy and enthusiasm that they bring to their work. This suggests that delivery riders are likely to feel vigorous and strong at work, with high physical and mental strength dedicated to their activities. Commitment has the highest mean score, suggesting that riders are highly likely to feel committed to the job, believe that their work is meaningful, and are proud of what they do. Absorption has the lowest mean; this indicates that delivery riders are usually completely focused and immersed in their job while making deliveries.

Table 2. Level of Work Engagement among Delivery Riders

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Vigor	0.90	4.57	High
Dedication	1.02	4.83	High
Absorption	0.95	4.39	High
Overall	0.82	4.57	High

These findings are consistent with the work of Schaufeli and Bakker (2003), who identified vigor, dedication, and absorption as core dimensions of work engagement and emphasized that high levels of these indicators reflect a motivated and committed workforce. Similarly, Jaya and Ariyanto (2021) found that simultaneously, vigor, dedication, and absorption have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Observations showed that employees exhibit considerable vigor, reflected by their high energy, enthusiasm, mental resilience, and persistence in fulfilling their responsibilities, despite unfavorable situations. Likewise, the dedication of the employees is shown by their sense of purpose, pride, enthusiasm, and inspiration from their work, reflecting a sense of significant attachment to their jobs. Furthermore, the standard deviation scores indicate that although the majority of delivery riders had similar levels of engagement, there were still differences in the degree to which they felt vigor, dedication, and absorption.

Significant Relationship between Job Stress and Work Engagement among Delivery Riders

Presented in Table 3 is the significant relationship between job stress and work engagement among delivery riders, and it manifested no relationship as revealed by the following result. The computed r-value of .073 and the p-

value of .472, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicate no significant relationship between the two variables. Consequently, the null hypothesis is accepted. This suggests that the work engagement of delivery riders is not influenced by their level of job stress. In other words, regardless of whether delivery riders experience high or low job stress, their level of work engagement remains unaffected. This further implies that other factors, rather than job stress, may contribute to their work engagement.

When examining the specific indicators which are the job stress having r- value of -.053 and p-value of .599; role expectation conflict having with r-value of -.099 and p-value of .326, and work-life balance having r-value of .188 and p-value of .061, yielded a results greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating no significant relationship with work engagement. As such, the null hypothesis is also accepted for these variables. These imply that delivery riders' work engagement is not significantly influenced by stress levels, inconsistencies in expected roles, or challenges in managing work-life boundaries.

In contrast, co-worker support demonstrated a significant relationship with work engagement, as disclosed by an r-value of .243 and a p-value of .015, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This means a rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating that co-worker support positively influences work engagement among delivery riders. Thus, co-worker support emerges as the only factor among those examined that has a significant relationship with their level of work engagement.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Job Stress and Work Engagement among Delivery Riders

Job Stress	Work Engagement			
	Vigor	Dedication	Absorption	Overall
Job Stress	.094 (.355)	.083 (.413)	-.043 (.671)	-.053 (.599)
Role Expectation Conflict	-.123 (.223)	-.038 (.707)	-.048 (.635)	-.099 (.326)
Co-worker Support	.110 (.278)	-.019 (.849)	.204* (.041)	.243* (.015)
Work-Life Balance	.448** (.000)	.376** (.000)	.229* (.022)	.188 (.061)
Overall	.187 (.062)	.155 (.123)	.108 (.286)	.073 (.472)

Presented in Table 4 is the result of the regression analysis. It can be seen from the table that the indicator co-worker support influences work engagement, as revealed in the p-value of 0.034, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. It implies that co-worker support among delivery riders can significantly influence work engagement. However, job stress, role expectation conflict, and work-life balance as indicators cannot predict work engagement; it also implies that it doesn't influence work engagement among delivery riders as reflected in the p-value of 0.865, 0.372, and 0.233, respectively. This indicates additionally that the three indicators being mentioned cannot influence work engagement, therefore, it has nothing to do with work engagement.

The r-square value or coefficient of determination is 0.088, equivalent to 8.8%, meaning that job stress can only influence work engagement by 8.8%. The variance, or the remaining 91.2%, is attributed to other factors not covered in the study. This implies further that there are many variables influential on the work engagement of the delivery riders, but not job stress.

Additionally, the f-value is 2.278, and the p-value is .066, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. This points to the fact that job stress cannot influence work engagement. The combination of such indicators cannot influence work engagement among delivery riders, further emphasizing that job stress has nothing to do with work engagement.

As can be deduced from Table 4, work engagement can be predicted using this particular equation:
 $WE = 3.188 + .023JS - .110REC + .280CWS + .140WLB$

Table 4. Domain of Job Stress Best Predicts Work Engagement

Job Stress	Work Engagement		
	Beta	t-value	p-value
Constant	3.188	4.861	.000
Job Stress	.023	.171	.865
Role Expectation Conflict	-.110	-.897	.372
Co-worker Support	.280	2.156	.034
Work-Life Balance	.140	1.201	.233
R Square = .088 or 8.8%			
F- Value = 2.278			
P- Value = .066			
WE= 3.188+.023JS-.110REC+.280CWS+.140WLB			

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study reveal that delivery riders experience a moderate level of job stress, particularly in terms of role expectation conflict, but benefit from high levels of co-worker support and work-life balance. Despite encountering workload pressures and unclear expectations, riders manage their stress relatively well due to strong peer support and effective time management. Notably, work engagement among delivery riders is consistently high across all dimensions, such as vigor, dedication, and absorption, indicating a highly motivated and resilient workforce. This suggests that delivery riders are not only capable of enduring the challenges of their job but also find meaning and satisfaction in their roles.

However, the statistical analysis shows no significant relationship between job stress and work engagement, implying that delivery riders' engagement at work is not influenced by the stress they experience. Among all variables examined, only co-worker support shows a significant positive influence on work engagement. This highlights the critical role of social support in maintaining high levels of motivation and performance.

The regression results reveal a complex relationship between work engagement and the studied factors (job stress, role expectation conflict, coworker support, and work-life balance) among delivery riders. While coworker support demonstrates a statistically significant positive correlation with work engagement ($p = 0.034$), the model's overall predictive power is weak ($R^2 = 0.088$). This indicates that only 8.8% of the variance in work engagement is explained by these four variables. The p-values for job stress ($p = 0.865$), role expectation conflict ($p = 0.372$), and work-life balance ($p = 0.233$) are all regarded as insignificant, and these are not significant predictors of work engagement in this model. The F-test value ($p = 0.066$) is also not significant and confirms that the combined effect of these variables is not a significant predictor of work engagement.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that delivery service providers focus on enhancing co-worker support to improve work engagement among delivery riders. Since co-worker support showed a statistically significant positive influence on work engagement, organizations should consider implementing initiatives that foster teamwork, peer communication, and mutual assistance among riders.

Team-building programs: Establish structured programs to encourage collaboration and support among delivery riders. This can include regular team meetings, collaborative activities, and mentorship opportunities. **Peer support systems:** Develop formal or informal support networks where riders can share challenges, provide advice, and assist each other in managing the pressures of the job. **Enhanced communication platforms:** Provide digital tools or apps that allow riders to communicate effectively, share experiences, and support each other in real time. **Recognition of teamwork:** Recognize and reward riders who demonstrate strong collaboration and help create a supportive atmosphere, thereby reinforcing the value of peer support.

Given the low predictive power of stress-related variables in influencing work engagement, these recommendations aim to capitalize on the elements that have a more direct impact on rider engagement and job satisfaction. Further research is recommended to explore additional factors, such as job autonomy, to further optimize work conditions and engagement.

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